

Seedling News

Distributed to the nursery and agricultural industry of southern Africa

September 1987

FROM SEED TO TABLE Where do you stand?

Planning begins before seed consideration.

To many farmers, the conversion of seed into a household commodity is not their concern. This is an unfortunate misconception since the grower of farm products can influence this process dramatically. *Seedling News*, with the assistance of Checkers Fresh Produce — Natal, Mr. J. Snaith of "Woodlands" and Mike's Kitchen, took a look at the seed to table story.

Contract production for the retail distributor is one of the many options open to today's vegetable growers. Market

agents (usually at the National Fresh Produce Markets), contracts for dehydrating, freezing and canning plants, direct to restaurants and the public, are some of the other options. Whichever option is chosen, adequate returns on investment are essential to remain in business.

Contract producers may have the option to cover forward on price. This gives closer tolerances for planning and allows for more accurate targets of costs and profits. Note that a contract is essentially selling the product **before** purchasing the seed. When planning for high quality produce, expect higher production costs and a greater management demand. However, the premium paid for quality decreases in direct proportion to the weight of produce on offer at any given time, but this effect is not so evident in the direct marketing process.

One of the main aims of direct marketing, such as contract production for the retail distributor, is the speed of distribution from harvest to the shopping basket. Minimum handling means reduced shrinkage, damage and direct labour costs. The producer very often has a greater impact on the produce which reaches the shopping basket — even to

Preparation and presentation add the finishing touch.

the extent of altering eating habits.

Whichever method you use in converting seed to a table product, a professional approach with sound practical knowledge and management are essential. Vegetables, possibly more than any other farm produce, are the cause of more financial problems than they have solved for inexperienced growers. ▼

Minimal handling and speedy deliveries retain crop quality.

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First Seedling Transplant Field Day

This was hosted by Royce Rosettenstein on his farm Killarney Estate, Tala Valley, and organised by the Seedling Growers Association of South Africa and the Department of Horticultural Science, University of Natal. With about 350 visitors from all over Southern Africa, the day was a resounding success.

Dave Biggs, Chairman of the Association, gave the welcoming address. The SGASA consists of about 50 grower members and 30 supply members spread throughout South Africa. These seedling growers are proud of their achievements. This is particularly justifiable when considering the short history of the industry and that their customers are the biggest potential competition should plant quality, service or price fail to satisfy. However, the considerable growth of the industry over the last few years is surely an indication of satisfactory meeting of the demand.

The seedling industry is an intensive, highly management and labour orientated industry reflecting the worldwide trend of specialization. The more technology employed, the easier it is for things to go wrong — seedling nurseries are no exception. For this reason, potential customers should shop around for nurseries with a reputation for reliability. A visit to the nursery is a good

idea. On this visit, some points to note are: quality and uniformity of seedlings in the nursery; hygiene and cleanliness measures; no related crops nearby; precautions against unfavourable weather conditions; no recycling of old growing medium; adequate tray sterilization; filtration (and possibly water treatment) with adequate reserves and standby equipment. Are adequate records kept with accurate labelling of varieties, can you discuss your seasons requirements well in advance and do you get a confirmation of your order? From the nurseryman's side, collection of seedlings by due date and timeous payment of accounts help tremendously in the smooth running of a nursery and containment of costs.

Future trends indicate continued growth in the seedling industry. Competition between nurseries is likely to increase with quality and service being the key. Ease of transport allows nurseries to supply long distances, 500 km being quite feasible. The continued development of crops such as tobacco in Natal, multiseeded onions (see Seedling News, March 1987), pastures (K11 and Kikuyu) as well as lawns show great potential, as does sugar cane. The continued addition of new crops to the range produced by seedling growers is a sure sign of a dynamic viable industry.

No room for mediocrity

Vito Rugani, M.D. of Markpo and Chairman of the SAAU Vegetable Committee gave the opening address. He noted the great increase in Speedling seedling usage by farmers and that the seedling nursery industry was settling down. Nothing must come between the farmer

Dave Biggs planting a lawn from Speedling.

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and the nurseryman, particularly when considering that the farmers livelihood is in the hands of the nurseryman. This requires quality, efficiency, cost control, innovation, service and reliability — not cheap seedlings. Farmers should take advantage of the seedling industry such as: speed of cropping from transplant to harvest with consequent reductions in number of cultivations and better fertilizer usage; better crop uniformity; phenomenal savings on seed costs thereby allowing for purchase of better quality seed and varieties; enforced planning of the farming operation. A farmer who plans becomes a successful farmer.

Although the seedling industry still has some rough patches — it is an active, vibrant industry free of fixed pricing — it has become a part of agriculture in South Africa.

Seedling Systems — an Overview

Dr. Irwin Smith, Dept. of Horticultural Science, University of Natal gave a slide presentation of the various seedling systems around the world. The Speedling system, probably the most popular in terms of seedling production and international usage, was started by George Todd. At that stage, he was a cauliflower grower convinced that more efficient methods of seedling production were possible. Many other planter flats are now available, most of them using the principles of individual cells for each seedling, air pruning of roots for stimulation of secondary roots, use of soilless growing medium and attention to fertilizer and water requirements. Alternative systems are the paper-pot and peat-block methods particularly popular in Japan and Europe respectively.

The continued growth of the seedling industry, from virtually nothing 15 years ago, is a reflection of the innovation of the planter flat system and the continued development of improved methods and technology.

Is it legal?

Ed Thunstron, (a lawyer), spoke on the implications of the Conditions of Trade Agreement drawn up for members of SGASA. This document was seen to be required in the light of previous legal wrangles with some customers. The agreement does not negate the common law rights of the purchaser, but rather sets out to specify the permissible tolerances. Note that seedling growers fall into the category of seller who are deemed to be experts. For this reason, a disappointed purchaser can recover not only the purchase price with interest, but consequential damages as well. Comparing the value of the seedlings to the expected profit on final yield, it is obvious that the seedling grower must protect his business. For these reasons, the 'confirmation of order form' containing the general conditions of trade, was drawn up.

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What about costs?

Dr. Irwin Smith, Dept. of Horticultural Science, University of Natal, discussed the costing of transplanting (planter flat and seed bed) and direct sowing. Whichever system is used, the cost of planting material is minor compared to the other production costs. Considering the impact planting material can have on final yield, it is probably worthwhile paying the premium for quality.

Possibly a major item in favour of nursery seedlings is that no management time for the farmer/forester is required. This then leaves time for looking after crops in the land without becoming involved in a different sphere of plant production. The tremendous swing towards specialist-grown seedlings suggests which side the costing favours.

Diseases under control

Mark Laing, Dept. of Plant Pathology, University of Natal considers the improved hygiene of nurseries compared to seedbeds on the farm to be a major factor contributing to a reduction of certain diseases. Black leg in cabbages is no longer considered to be a serious threat. Spread of soil borne diseases such as club root, bacterial wilt and canker is reduced by not planting out contaminated seedlings. As most nursery seedlings are not produced next to field crops, spread of many diseases from the crops to the seedlings is less likely. Viral diseases are particularly affected by these measures.

Greater uniformity of the crop from using the more uniform nursery seedlings means that crop residues are left on the land for a shorter time and a reduced number of harvests reduces the spread of disease within the field. It is common for the number of cabbage harvests to be reduced from 5-9 cuts to 1-3 by using nursery transplants. Better than 90% first cut is not unheard of.

Nurseries are not without their problems. Three which merit special attention are damping-off, downy mildew and bacterial speck/spot. However, note

that these are foliar diseases largely controlled by appropriate management rather than the far more serious soil-borne diseases.

It is clear, particularly regarding the Natal cabbage crop, that the use of speedlings and the elimination of crop debris are the two most important management practices in the control of all soil-borne and many foliar diseases of vegetables.

One of the transplanting machines being put through its paces.

Packaging — functional and attractive

Ian Stuart, Nampak, gave a slide presentation showing some of the different applications where corrugated cardboard containers have proved their value. Many seedling nurseries are using cardboard containers for the delivery of seedlings. The containers protect seedlings from the environment as well as allowing a large number of seedlings to be transported since they are easily stacked. The containers are disposable and therefore reduce disease spread in seedlings, as well as reducing the chance of diseases spreading from the farm back to the nursery.

Cardboard container technology was

easily adapted to fill the need identified by the seedling industry. A disposable, economical container able to withstand the problems associated with transporting a fragile, wet commodity was readily designed. As with all packaging, the container also conveys an image. Customized corrugated cardboard containers have been another step in the professional approach for many nurseries.

Mechanization in the field

Simon Cooper, Division of Agricultural Engineering, Dept. of Agriculture, discussed the trends in field mechanization. The greatest attention has been to improve direct sowing of extensive crops such as maize. The necessity for mechanization arose from the need to complete the operation in a limited time. Horticultural crops have been much slower to develop mechanization largely due to the smaller areas planted and the wide range of seed sizes and shapes.

Seedling transplanting machinery has suffered from the same constraints as the direct sowing machinery. However, new developments are being investigated due to the relatively larger areas being planted to transplants. This machinery can utilise some of the research conducted for extensive field crops, in particular attachment and tractor types, methods of soil preparation and simultaneous applications of water and fertilizer.

Mechanized transplanting offers the advantages of quicker and more accurate crop establishment than manual transplanting. There is no need to prepare a fine seedbed, with the elimination of the sensitive germination to emergence period, transplanting can be done at higher soil moisture levels than seed drills will allow and competition from weeds is greatly reduced compared to direct sowing. Seedling selection and improved accuracy of placement means accurate plant populations and an even maturation of the crop.

Nursery considerations

Dave Barbour, Forestry Services Nursery, looked at the relationships between the nurseryman and his customers. He noted that the seedling industry is a new discipline with its own set of rules, but attention to detail and professionalism on both sides are important to success. The professional should have the experience and ability to produce a good product consistently.

Price cutting is the only selling advantage for the nursery-under-a-tree, possible only because of the low overheads. This is shown dramatically when comparing the Transvaal and Natal nursery industries. Natal vegetable farmers and foresters have the very real benefits of a healthy nursery industry whereas in the Transvaal, where price cutting has been the order of the day, quality and service can only have suffered badly.

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Processors, being large buyers of seedlings, can have a large impact on the seedling industry. Where nurseries have been played off against one another to get the cheapest price, some real let-downs occur when nurseries bite off more than they can chew. Price should be the last criterion to the processors at this stage, especially in the Cape with their fledgling nursery industry. Second hand seedlings in old banana boxes are just not good enough. In the not too distant future, the more advanced nurseryman will have technical representatives out on the road selling and advising.

What of the availability of technical information to both the grower and the nurseryman? Starke Ayres must be complimented for their efforts with *Seedling News*, but this will unfortunately always be restricted to in-house matters. Foresters are fortunate to have an independent publication, *SA Forestry* which has been an immediate success. The vegetable industry needs an equivalent of the *American Vegetable Grower*, published by an independent publisher. *(The editor would appreciate readers comments on this).*

User comments

Conrad Rottcher, one of the first of Natal vegetable farmers to use nursery seedlings, pointed out to nurserymen where they could improve their service. He noted that when he was introduced to plug seedlings, peat was being used as

the growing medium, with excellent root growth. Since nurseries had changed to a locally produced medium, root growth and plug formation were not as good. Poor root growth results in seedlings suffering some transplant shock, whereas the early seedlings suffered no setback. Root growth only in the top segment of the plug is a problem. This might be due to small, daily applications of nutrients. (Probably more closely related to too frequent small applications of water which do not wet the whole plug volume — editor). These seedlings do not transplant easily and are prone to shock.

Other problems experienced by farmers are caused by incorrect or mixed varieties, seedlings not ready on due date, excessively soft and lanky plants, inaccurate seedling counts, and delivery of diseased seedlings. Transport of seedlings can sometimes cause problems when the seedlings arrive with their root plugs dried out. This is particularly a problem with seedlings near the hand-holds in the containers.

After the talks, visitors could observe a wide range of crops transplanted into the demonstration plots. These included cabbages, tomatoes, swiss chard, multi-seeded onions, beetroot, many flowers, gum, pine, wattle and shelterbelt trees, sugar cane and pasture grasses. Various irrigation innovations and mini-tunnels/cloches were demonstrated as well as field preparation and mechanical transplanting equipment. ▼

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Land Preparation

—The Key to Success

The soil is more than just a supporting structure for plant growth. Soil is the vital source of minerals, air and water. For successful plant growth, it is imperative that the soil structure must aid plant roots in their quest for essential nutrients.

Nowhere in agriculture is the soil effect more pronounced than in the delicate seed germination stage. At this time, levels of moisture, air and soluble salts are critical. Many physical factors of soil structure can have a profound

effect on these levels. While soil tillth is commonly recognised as having a major effect on the success of direct sown operations, the improvement in seedling growth after transplanting into correctly prepared land must not be ignored.

The effect of soil clod sizes becomes more pronounced the smaller the seed or seedlings planted. Depth and adequate soil contact are critical in supplying sufficient soil moisture and protection from the heat of the sun. The figures show clearly the result of excessively large clod sizes on seed placement in the soil. For seedlings, those where the root plug is exposed to the sun as well as those with poor soil contact will show poor growth and may die.

Planning of vegetable crops is imperative to the successful marketing of that crop. With an emphasis on planned production, uniformity of growth and production in the field are highly desirable. A uniformly well-prepared land is an essential prerequisite for uniformity in seed germination, seedling growth and subsequent crop.

Bemark u?

Die woord *bemaking* beteken vir verskillende mense verskillende dinge. Dit kom van Latyn *merces* (beloning) of *merx* (handelsware), en behels duidelik 'n proses van die verkoop van goedere. Vir baie mense is bemarking bloot 'n ander naam vir 'verkoop' of 'n spoggerige naam vir 'advertering'. Dit is baie beperkte definisies vir die hele reeks bedrywighede wat te doen het met die winsgewende identifisering, antiserping en bevrediging van klantebehoefes.

As u vind dat u normaalweg net ontslae raak van wat u plaas produseer, bemark u nie. Hierdie siklus van oorvoering en tekort dui op of 'n seisoenale produk of swak produksiebeplanning. Daar is min werklik seisoenale produkte — hoofsaaklik weens die wisselende klimaat in die produksiegebiede en die wye verskeidenheid kultivars wat tans beskikbaar is.

Beplanning is waarskynlik die belangrikste boerderypraktik. Akkurate be-

Grondvoorbereiding het 'n opmerklike uitwerking op plantgroe. Klontgrootte bepaal die hoeveelheid kontak tussen die grond en die saad/saailing, sowel as eenvormigheid van plasing in die grond.

planning verg geskikte rekords — nie net van jou eie plaas nie, maar ook van buite-invloede wat jou besluite mag af-fekteer. Produksie moet volgens ver-eistes beplan word, en dan in verband gebring word met die fisiese beperkinge en die winsgewendheid wat deur jou eie landerye getoon word. Stel vas waarom jou potensiele klante jou produk mag wil hê — jy sal effektiewer meeding as jou produk meer klantebehoefte bevredig.

Identifiseer mededingende produkte. Ander produsente van dieselfde produk is ooglopende mededingers, maar ont-hou dat alle aankope uiteindelik van die-selfde bron kom — die koper se beskik-bare geld. Om jou produk hoër-op op die aankoopprioriteitslys te kry, is belangrik.

Aankoopprioriteit is 'n weerspieëling van produkbeeld. Is dit noodsaaklik? Indien nie, is dit belangrik en kan ek dit bekostig? Gehalte en prys is belangrike kriteria by die bepaling van klante-tevredenheid. Terwyl hoë gehalte en lae pryse selde saamval, is die teendeel on-gelukkig te dikwels die geval. Waar klante geruk is met 'n hoë prys en teleur-gestel is deur swak gehalte, kan dit toekomstige aankoop van die produk verongeluk.

Dit is nie maklik om klantevereistes vooruit te bepaal nie, weens faktore soos die grootte van die mark, die soorte produkte wat beskikbaar is, en die 'skop' van nuwe vraag.

Wat u produkte ook al mag wees — groente, 'Johannesburg Goud', hout — noukeuriger aandag aan alle aspekte van bemaking sal jou eindsyfer ver-beter. ▼

What Value Quality?

No matter how good vegetables are on the land, they have no profit value unless they are sold profitably. The production of quality produce is a skilled operation. This function is clearly the responsibility of the grower. What about preserving that quality right through the market place and on to the table?

The maintenance of quality through-out the distribution process is related to a number of practices. Some are directly in the hands of the grower — others are controlled by the distributor. Speed of distribution from the time of harvest to the shopping basket is vital.

Maintenance of produce at a reason-able temperature will prolong vegetable quality. This can be achieved by harvest-ing before the produce gains field heat,

harvest early in the day — or even at night! Removal of field heat is a more ex-pensive option — often associated with cooling equipment. This option is used mainly by distributors, but even when refrigerated trucks are used, harvest-ing before field heat accumulates is desir-able. Cooler temperatures and pro-tection from sunlight are essential to prolong vegetable shelf life.

Careful product handling and reduc-ing handling to a minimum will reduce losses through bruising. Field packing may be preferable to repacking produce in the shed. The system of packing into crates which are delivered at the retail store reduces handling considerably. Training of produce handlers must be conducted along the whole chain. As

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with maintaining cool temperatures — one break in the chain will negate all benefits of careful on-farm handling.

There are very few consumers who are happy to buy vegetables of varying quality. Correct grading of vegetables adds value. The placing of poorer grades beneath the better quality in a pocket or carton is a marketing trick guaranteed to dissatisfy customers.

Packaging of produce is another value-adding option. The standard sizes of packaging traditional at National Fresh Produce Markets are patently inconvenient for the majority of vegetable purchasers. Supermarkets and green-grocers often offer prepacked and loose produce. Where farm packing is good, most retail outlets will sell the produce in that packaging. This offers the farmer a direct contact with the ultimate customer where tips on storage, preparation and nutrient content can be passed on.

Vegetables are one of the few commodities offered on a free market. Without any controlling body, it is up to the producers and distributors to ensure that their produce is presented to the purchaser in an attractive manner. This involves the use of innovative presentation and all of the more common marketing methods.

Produce	°C
Brinjal	10-13
Courgette	10-14
Cucumbers	7-10
Green beans	5-10
Peppers	5-10
Spinach	2-5
Sweet melons	4-7
Tomatoes — green	13-16
Tomatoes — pink	10-14

Optimum transport and display temperatures for maximum shelf life and quality maintenance.

While efficient management coupled with good variety choice mean a greater chance of meeting consumer requirements, consumption of vegetables will only be improved with a better image of vegetables and an improved consumer perception of vegetable desirability. Educational promotions and high quality standards from seed to table are essential. ▼

Gedeeltelike wortelvervorming weens lugholte

'n Interessante wortelgroei patroon kom voor wanneer daar by die plant van saailingwortelprope 'n lugholte onder die prop gelaat word. Dit word veroorsaak wanneer daar in 'n gleufgat geplant word, soos wanneer die punt van 'n graaf, of 'n te skerp holtedrukker gebruik word om die gat te maak. So 'n lugholte sal waarskynliker in swaarder grond voorkom, maar omdat min plante gewoonlik gelig word om wortelgroei na te gaan, is die erns van gevolglike wortelvervorming nog nie behoorlik geëvalueer nie.

Hierdie besondere soort groei is deur die huidige SAKV-voorsitter, mnr. Richard Hill, by die Redhill Superplant Kwekery waargeneem. By hierdie kwekery word sade van sagtevrugtebome voorafontkiem en in Speedling-laaie gekweek voor uitplanting vir finale verkoop as uit-die-grond oorplantings. Dit is 'n ideale toestand vir die nagaan van wortelvorm, omdat alle plante in die bedryfproses opgegrawe word. Terwyl die paar wortels wat hierdie ongewone groei vertoon, nie juis as 'n probleem gesien word nie, is daar beter oorplanteg-

Die diagram toon die wortelgroei deur die lugholte wat by uitplanting geskep word, in vergelyking met groei sonder lugholte.

nieke ingevoer. Dit behels die gebruik van 'n holtedrukker wat 'n gaatjie maak waar geen lugholtes om die prop gelaat word nie.

Is hierdie wortelgroei deur die lugholte van groot belang? Waarskynlik nie, maar dit kan gerus by planting in gedagte gehou word, veral met die holtedrukker metode. 'n Verwante groeipatroon mag voorkom waar saailinge ná diepploeging uitgeplant word, waar lugholtes algemeen is. Miskien kan iemand in die bosboubedryf kommentaar lewer? ▼

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SEEDLING SIZES

— how do they compare?

The decision as to which size seedlings to buy is often based on intuition rather than fact. However, with a little more understanding of the relevant factors, this choice can be made to match seedling size more closely to your own management requirements.

It is important to distinguish between seedling size and age. One of the main problems of growing seedlings in a restricted area, whether in trays or seedbeds, is that yield potential is markedly inhibited by allowing the seedlings to become stressed by keeping them for too long before transplanting. How long is too long? This depends on the type of seedling and the growing conditions. This age factor is therefore related to the size of tray used for seedlings — the smaller the size, the sooner the seedlings will fill the available space.

This is where problems arise when nurseries change to trays with more cells. From previous experience, most farmers (and nurserymen) have a mental image of the size of seedling desired. In many instances, this image is derived from experience with seedbed seedlings. To obtain a seedling of adequate size but without losing yield potential means matching the growing conditions to the desired size.

Mismatches commonly occur. The main effect is to delay and reduce yields. This effect is particularly noticeable in crops where the main bulk of the plant is the yield — cabbage, lettuce etc. In crops which have a chance to recover from initial setbacks, (most research has been conducted on tomatoes), the final yield is delayed but not significantly different, but initial yield is markedly reduced.

Choice of tray model is primarily related to the surface area a seedling requires to achieve satisfactory size. This is usually expressed as plants per square metre. The cut-off number is quite accurate, but will vary according to the type and size of seedlings. The volume of each cell is a secondary factor related more to the shape of the seedling.

Greenhouse tomato seedlings grown

at densities of up to 320 plants/m² were shorter and more sturdy than seedlings grown at higher densities. In this experiment, all seedlings were grown for an equal length of time. At higher densities, initial tomato yields were reduced by up to 50% although final yield was similar. A very similar effect is obtained by using the same seedling density (550 plants/m²) but keeping some seedlings in the nursery for a longer period. Under these conditions, cabbages show a reduction in yield if seedlings are held in the nursery for too long. A yield reduction of up to 25% is likely.

Clearly it is not possible to specify exactly which model tray should be used and for how long seedlings should be kept in the nursery. However, experimentation and general experience can give a good idea of the best models to use for particular crops. In this regard, it is interesting to note how many farmers are requesting cole crop seedlings grown in model 128 trays. Obviously the smaller size seedlings are more difficult to cope with in the field, with resultant unacceptably high mortality rates.

The relationship between depth of tray and plant density is a further refine-

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Groentesaailinge van hoogstaande gehalte word van gesertifiseerde saad gekweek. Saailinge word alleenlik op bestelling voorsien. Alle bastersaadkopkool word teen R20 per duisend (saad ingesluit) voorsien. Pryslys kan op navraag voorsien word.

Saailinge word in 'n temperatuur- en vogbeheerde kweekhuis gekweek om te verseker dat saailinge gehard raak en oor 'n goed ontwikkelde wortelstelsel beskik.

NEW

NURSERYMEN

Improve your point of sale seedling image with the new disposable seedling punnets. Available in 20 cells with 12 and 6 cells set to come on stream shortly.

 STARKE AYRES

Model	Plants/m ²	Plant area (cm ²)	Cell volume (ml)	Area: Volume (cm ² /ml)
72	310	32,30	100	0,32
98	421	23,73	66	0,36
128/90	550	18,17	52	0,35
128	550	18,17	36	0,51
200	860	11,63	22	0,53
338	1 453	6,88	7,5	0,92

Characteristics of Speedling trays. Note the large area to volume ratio for model 338—suited to the general shape of very young seedlings. As the overall size of the seedlings increases, so can the area to volume ratio decrease to accommodate the altered growth shape of seedlings.

ment. The normal sizes of Speedling trays have been tested and proven satisfactory for most seedlings. However, there are some crops which exhibit a markedly stronger root growth. To cater for these seedlings, a greater depth relative to plant density may be desirable. In the main, tobacco, forestry and rooted cuttings prefer a deeper rooting volume. Most vegetable seedlings have cramped leafy growth by the time their weaker root systems have filled the plug. Using the rule that a seedling is ready for transplanting when its roots have bound the growing medium into a firm plug does not hold if the plug volume is not balanced with plant density. Lettuce is often quicker from sowing to heading in model 128 compared to model 200 trays

— this is a reflection of a relatively weak root system.

What size seedlings are the best? The larger the seedling, the easier it is to handle and the less transplanting stress will occur. However, provided seedlings are not too old (physiological — not chronological age) and transplanting conditions are suitable, even very small seedlings have been successful. Larger seedlings are generally desirable when extremes of temperatures are experienced.

To get the most out of your Speedlings, it is essential to match the tray size with the seedling size desired. The model 200 has proven to be the most popular for most vegetable seedlings, with a strong trend towards model 128 for summer and winter transplanting. ▼

Meganiese uitplanting

Huidiglik beskikbare uitplanteenhede het gewoonlik ernstige beperkinge, o.a. 'n lae vermoë (60–80 plante per minuut per eenheid), die feit dat 'n persoon die saailinge op die masjien moet hanteer, beperkinge na gelang van grondtoestande, en dikwels 'n slegs kleinerige mate van veiligheid vir die plante tydens hantering.

Instplant Limited, Israel, beweer dat hulle 'n prototipe uitplantmasjien ontwerp het sonder hierdie beperkinge. Tot vyf planteenhede oor twee meter, met

onafhanklike hoogstebeheer; unieke gronddeurdringestegnologie wat planting in alle grondsoorte toelaat — selfs tydens reën sowel as deur plastiek-molm; tempo's van 350 saailinge per minuut per eenheid teen 'n werkspoed van tot 4 km/h — dit is waarop vir dié masjien aanspraak gemaak word.

G'n wonder die masjien het 'n eerste prys in die 1986 Agritech-uitstalling verower nie. Instplant Ltd. soek nog na 'n geskikte vervaardiger om hierdie uitplanter te maak en te bemark. ▼

SNIPPETS

Battling to sow seed, but do not grow sufficient quantities to warrant buying a sowing machine? Why not approach a nursery which has a machine to plant for you? Apart from helping pay off the machine, you will also get the benefits of the uniformity and speed of sowing possible with a machine.

* * * *

Erratic seed germination — particularly in vigorous crops such as cabbage and lettuce — is closely related to temperatures during germination and the depth of sowing. Remember that the temperature affecting the seed is the medium, and not ambient, temperature. Depth of sowing can be made uniform by dibbling with an accurate dibbler such as the drum dibbler now available. At below R300, this hand operated unit (much like a rolling pin) is within reach of all nurserymen — available for model 128 and 200 trays.

* * * *

South African seed production is increasing by leaps and bounds. With plenty of land in low humidity areas, a sophisticated road and water distribution network, South Africa is an obvious choice for bulking of seed. South Africa — via the Starke Ayres Seed Production Division — is a major producer of hybrid carrot seed for the world market.

* * * *

Green Star — arguably the best cabbage cultivar for warm season heading — had a poor season last year due to seed problems. Growers will be relieved to know that not only is this a thing of the past, but the new seed crop has also been graded. This should be of particular interest to the seedling growers.

* * * *

Timber growers look set for a good demand for their product. Not only is demand for paper, wood for housing and local fuel requirements increasing but demand for exports of pulp, chips and charcoal is also on the increase. For a country with virtually no indigenous forest, this is quite a feat. Congratulations to CTC on extending their wood chip export contract.

* * * *

If previous trends are repeated, local demand for vegetables is likely to increase dramatically. However, just as the U.S. farmers have had to improve their ability to deliver a fresh product to the end buyer, so will local vegetable growers. Freshness and crispness are what really sell fresh vegetables says Joe Carcione, known as "The Greengrocer" to American television viewers.

* * * *

Onion transplants as multi-seeded plugs are relatively new. *Seedling News* would like to hear from readers, nurserymen and farmers, about their experiences with them.

EDITOR'S VIEW

Once again, the arrival of spring has spurred nurserymen into a flurry of activity. The growth of Speedling in South Africa took on a new meaning with the first National Seedling Transplant Day and continued expansion into new areas — particularly onions, pasture and sugar cane and a few lesser known crops such as guayule (a drought-tolerant plant which produces natural rubber). Asparagus Speedlings are effecting tremendous savings for farmers — mainly because of their exceptional vigour and a reduction in time to first harvest.

On the forestry side, continued demand for timber means a continued demand for forestry Speedlings. These have proven themselves over many years of planting to the extent that Speedling may now be regarded as the standard means of afforestation. Clonal forestry is a new concept of plant propagation since the clonal hedges are expected to provide cuttings all year. Research efforts are showing the way and initial setbacks are steadily being overcome. A new development on the horizon is the potential of clonal forestry with the ease of seed handling by using somatic embryos.

A new field for expansion of Speedling is that of landscaping. In most cases, landscapers are responsible for the layout and establishment of plants. The benefits of Speedling will therefore be obvious for reducing — potentially eliminating — plant mortality, and as a system for producing large numbers of plants economically. Lawn establishment projects may borrow from pasture farmers for the rapid establishment of lawns, particularly by vegetative propa-

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Business e.g. — forestry, vegetable farmer, seedling grower etc.
Besigheid bv. — bosbou, groenteboer, saailing kweker ens.

gation. Establishment on steep banks — such as roadside cuttings — may prove quicker and more effective using plugs.

Seedling nurseries may therefore be considered to have a bright future. However, quality plants and service are the name of the game. Already the industry has matured to the extent that it is much more expensive/difficult to establish a nursery than two or so years ago. The level of sophistication demanded has risen considerably, as has the level of expectation of seedling performance. It is one thing producing erratic quality when the farmer is just experimenting with the new system, but quite another to sabotage his whole production.

While a better understanding of growth requirements of seedlings is continuing, this is merely serving to refine methods. Basic good management

is essential. This entails the keeping of adequate records, knowing what is occurring in the nursery and maintaining a productive relationship with employees. In this regard, Arnold Mol's book "Motivating your farm labourer" is strongly recommended.

This *Seedling News* is largely dealing with the concept of marketing. While the examples have been mainly from the vegetable sector, the basic principles remain the same regardless of the product.

Now is the time, at the beginning of a new growing season, to resolve to improve on management and marketing skills. To win in an even match, you only need to make fewer mistakes. *Seedling News* wishes all in the seedling industry — growers and users alike — the best of the new season. ▼

Excessive seedling damage?

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Root penetration — Seedling damage
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VEGETABLE VARIETIES

—A marketing decision

Vegetable growers not only have a wide choice of type of vegetable, but also a large number of varieties of each type. Naturally, the more common vegetables offer a wider selection of varieties than the specialty types. With, for example, well over one hundred cabbage varieties

to choose from, how does one decide?

Decide first what is required by the customer. There is no point producing first class Brussels Sprouts if customers actually want broccoli. Then decide what type of vegetable is required — for example round, spitz or red cabbages.

All the popular vegetable types are available in a number of basic forms. Then look at specific preferences for colour, flavour, shape, texture and keeping quality.

This activity is all part of the planning stage to determine customer requirements. An expensive public survey is not necessary to determine this. Simply keeping in touch with market agents, restaurateurs, supermarket buyers, processing company and seed company representatives will give a good idea of what is desirable.

Time of production is another important factor. Some vegetables show a marked seasonal requirement — or the usage of that vegetable changes according to the season. Lettuce is in far greater demand in summer, while cauliflower and broccoli tend to be preferred in the cooler months. Probably the most important factor is producing good quality and maintaining that quality through to the end user.

Once these requirements are known, an inspection of seed catalogues and discussions with seed representatives will help in deciding on the variety best suited to the production capability of your lands. Confidence in matching varieties to seasonal and area conditions comes from extensive testing of varieties. In order to provide customers with a better service, Starke Ayres maintain an on-going research programme to screen introductions and also semi-commercial trials to confirm the basic research findings. These semi-commercial trials by farmers in all the production areas form a vital link in the introduction of new varieties. The benefit for farmers comes from an earlier awareness of improved varieties.

Novelty items are particularly popular with smallholders and prepackers who tend to market directly through green-grocers and other retail outlets. A problem with these limited demand items is the availability of seed. Current legislation prevents the importation of commercial quantities of seed unless the variety is registered with the Department. Since very few varieties are bred locally, this legislation is effective for most vegetable crops required in very limited quantities.

The slogan "The difference is research" could very well be applied to the vegetable industry. The better a variety is known, the more confident one can be in recommending or planting that variety. Research is the link of confidence.

RESEARCH

THE LINK OF CONFIDENCE

Research at Greytown, Letsitele, Delmas and Constantia.

Few businesses have the link of confidence between seller and buyer as the seedsman and his customers. Quality and trueness to type can seldom be determined by the naked eye. Differences such as maturity, colour, plant height, productivity, disease tolerances, and many other inheritable qualities are not apparent through observation of the seed itself. At Starke-Ayres, we have built up this link of confidence between ourselves and our customers.

Why?

Because we believe in research and thoroughly testing our seed *before* we sell it to you.

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